

The Impact of Learning Motivation and Learning Activeness for the Result of Social Subject in SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to obtain knowledge regarding the influence of student learning motivation and learning activeness on student learning outcomes in social studies subjects for class VIII students at SMP Negeri Pematang Siantar. This type of research is quantitative research with a quantitative descriptive data analysis approach with the testing media used is Microsoft Excel . The total population in this study was 146 students. The sample collection technique used was the Slovin formula. The data collection technique used was a questionnaire. Hypothesis data collection techniques use simple regression analysis, multiple regression analysis and coefficient of determination (R^2). The results of this study state that: 1) There is a positive and significant influence of learning motivation on learning outcomes , this result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of learning motivation (0.02) > t table value (1.690) which means that this variable is significant. 2) There is a positiv and significant influence on student learning activity on learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of student learning activity (3.66 > t table value (0.334) which means this variable is significant. 3) Learning motivation and student learning activity together influence learning outcomes, this result can be seen in the F test where the calculated F value (1140.14) > table F value (0.334). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.971, which means that 97.1% of the variables of student motivation and active learning have an influence on student learning outcomes at the SM P Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar school, and the remaining 2.9% is the influence of variables that were not studied. in this research .

INTRODUCTION

Education is an important factor in the development and development of a country. The country is said to be advanced in all fields, whether economic, technological or other, inseparable from the role of education. This is because intelligent or educated people will be able to make a positive contribution to the country. However, what needs to be remembered is that education will be maximally successful when every element of education, from bottom to top, is always oriented towards national education goals.

The aim of education is to form high quality human resources so that they become human beings who have faith and are devoted to God Almighty who are able to face the development of the times with the help of the role of a teacher in educating children's intellectual and moral abilities. Internal factors are factors that originate from the individual while external factors are factors that originate from outside the individual or the environment. Meanwhile, the main causes of learning problems are external factors, including: in the form of wrong learning strategies, management of learning activities that do not arouse children's learning motivation, as well as environmental factors that greatly influence the learning outcomes achieved by students.

Based on observations that researchers have made at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar, teachers always provide motivation and direction to students before and after learning, but there are still students who are not interested in learning optimally, because these students are lazy about learning, so very influential on student learning outcomes. This can be seen from the Mid-Semester Assessment in Social Sciences subjects. Information is obtained that the learning outcomes in Social Sciences subjects are in In class VIII there are still some students whose scores are below the KKM, amounting to 63% or 141 students, while those whose scores are above the KKM are 37% or as many as 82 students. From the results of the assessment at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar, the mid -semester assessment of class VIII students shows that learning outcomes are still low . According to one of the teachers interviewed by researchers, students are still less active and do not dare to ask the teacher if they do not understand the material/lessons presented by the teacher, are silent when answering questions from the teacher, and are not motivated to present and explain a problem by providing a discussion. about the problem given.

According to Uno (2013:23), learning motivation is an urge that arises in a person consciously or unconsciously to carry out an action with a specific goal. Learning motivation can be classified into two, namely :

1. Intrinsic motivation (circumstances that originate from within the student himself which can encourage him to take learning actions)
2. Extrinsic motivation (circumstances that come from outside the individual student that encourage him to carry out learning activities).

From the results of observations at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar, it was found that students' motivation to learn was lacking. Students do not have the confidence to provide rebuttals or responses to questions given by the teacher and there is no concentration and curiosity about things conveyed by the teacher and difficulties in learning are considered by students as challenges that must be overcome even though difficulties in learning are a problem. Motivate students to be more active in every lesson to obtain satisfactory results for better grades.

Next, it's not just motivation supporting in achieving good learning results, active learning is also one of the supports that should not be missed. From the results of the researcher's observations when learning activities were taking place there were

still many students who were less active in participating in learning activities, for example, students looked less cheerful, for example, shown by a less than cheerful face. fit or moody, students do not respond when the teacher asks a question even though the question is easy, for example material that has often been discussed, then students tend to always talk behind their back when the teacher explains the lesson in front of the class. So there is a lack of student learning activeness when learning activities are taking place, there are students who just sit quietly and when the teacher asks questions students do not dare to answer the questions.

So based on the low learning activity of students, there is a need for research on internal and external factors that cause low student learning activity. So from the problems above , the factors that are thought to influence the learning outcomes of class VIII students focus on learning motivation and learning activity . If these factors are not ignored, it will affect the learning outcomes of each student at school .

The results from the researcher's observations of the problem description above are clear that learning motivation and learning activity are the dominant factors in determining students' success in carrying out their learning activities, to achieve good learning outcomes. So the researcher was interested in conducting research with the title " The Influence of Learning Motivation and Student Learning Activeness on Student Learning Outcomes in Social Sciences Subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar " .

THEORETICAL REVIEW

1. Motivation to learn

According to Uno (2013:23), learning motivation is internal and external encouragement for students who are studying to make changes in behavior, generally with several indicators or supporting elements. Internal and external encouragement in students arises due to intrinsic factors and extrinsic factors. Intrinsic factors can be the desire and desire to succeed and encouragement of the need to learn, hope for ideals, while extrinsic factors are the presence of awards, a conducive learning environment and interesting learning activities. Based on the opinions of these experts, the author can understand that what is meant by learning motivation is motivation that is able to provide encouragement to students to learn and carry out lessons by providing predetermined direction or goals.

2. Learning Activeness

Sadirman (2014: 100) states that active learning is activity that is related to the physical and mental, namely doing and thinking as a series that cannot be separated. From the opinions of the experts above, it can be concluded that active learning is an activity or activity given to students, both physical and non-physical, during the learning process so that students are expected to be able to develop their potential and achieve the desired learning outcomes.

3. Learning outcomes

Susanto (2017:5) states that learning outcomes can be interpreted as the level of success of students in studying subject matter at school which is expressed in the scores obtained from test results regarding a certain amount of subject matter. Based on the experts' explanations, it can be concluded that learning outcomes are abilities as well as changes in attitudes and behavior as well as skills that can be identified through evaluation and assessment activities after students experience the learning process.

METHODS

Method The research used is a quantitative research approach. This research is descriptive, namely a research method that accurately describes the conditions that occur regarding the facts, characteristics and relationships between the conditions being studied. Thus, quantitative data is described in words to obtain accurate and reliable research results .

Based on the researcher's title "The Influence of Learning Motivation and Student Learning Activeness on Student Learning Outcomes in Class VIII Social Sciences Subjects at SMP NEGERI 7 Pematang Siantar" . This research was carried out at SMPN 7 Pematang Siant ar from July to October 2023 . The population in this study were all students in class VIII of SMPN 7 Pematang Siantar 7 classes totaling 223 students . The sample in this research was 146 students.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Result

Instrument Validity Test

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire or questionnaire is valid or not. The examiner to determine whether a questionnaire or questionnaire is valid or not, namely by comparing the value of r_{count} with r_{table} . If $r_{count} > r_{table}$ at a significant level of 95% or $\alpha = 5\%$, then the statement on the questionnaire or questionnaire is said to be valid .

Items that are declared valid are items that have a correlation value $(r) > 0.324$, while items that have a correlation value $(r) > 0.324$ are items valid question . This can be concluded that for the questions it is known that there are 40 items that have a correlation value $(r) > 0.324$ and as many as 4 questions $(r) < 0.324$, it is known that 36 questions have valid data and 4 are invalid. Therefore, the 4 invalid questions were not used for further research .

Instrument Reliability Test

For the questionnaire reliability criteria, if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ with a significant level ($\alpha = 0.05$) then the questionnaire is said to be reliable. However, if $r_{count} \leq r_{table}$ then the question is considered to have no reliability. If the Cronbach Alpha value is > 0.60 it is said to be reliable, but if the Cronbach Alpha value is < 0.60 it is said to be unreliable.

From the data obtained , 0.9190 and 0.8992, the r_{table} obtained = 0.324. So $r_{count} > r_{table}$ and if the Cronbach Alpha value (0.9190 and 8992) > 0.324 . From the results of calculating the reliability of learning motivation and learning activeness, it can be concluded that the instruments in the questionnaire used are reliable.

Test Data Analysis Techniques

Data Normality Test

Table 1. Normality Test Results

Amount	Fo	fh	(Fo-fh)	(fo-fh)^2	X^2
47	4	5,615	-1,615	2,6095	0,4647
48	5	5,615	-0,615	0,3787	0,067439
52	4	5,615	-1,615	2,6095	0,4647
54	2	5,615	-3,615	13,0710	2,327713
55	10	5,615	4,385	19,2249	3,423604
56	12	5,615	6,385	40,7633	7,25922
57	3	5,615	-2,615	6,8402	1,218124
58	4	5,615	-1,615	2,6095	0,4647
59	8	5,615	2,385	5,6864	1,012645
60	5	5,615	-0,615	0,3787	0,067439
61	5	5,615	-0,615	0,3787	0,067439
62	4	5,615	-1,615	2,6095	0,4647
63	4	5,615	-1,615	2,6095	0,4647
64	17	5,615	11,385	129,609	23,08114
66	5	5,615	-0,615	0,3787	0,067439
67	5	5,615	-0,615	0,3787	0,067439
68	5	5,615	-0,615	0,3787	0,067439
69	9	5,615	3,385	11,4556	2,040042
70	3	5,615	-2,615	6,8402	1,218124
71	4	5,615	-1,615	2,6095	0,4647
72	4	5,615	-1,615	2,6095	0,4647
74	2	5,615	-3,615	13,0710	2,327713
75	5	5,615	-0,615	0,3787	0,067439
76	8	5,615	2,385	5,6864	1,012645
79	4	5,615	-1,615	2,6095	0,4647
86	4	5,615	-1,615	2,6095	0,4647
87	1	5,615	-4,615	21,3018	3,793467
	146				53,36881

The Kolmogorov Smirnov value for the learning motivation variable is $0.53.36881 > 0.05$, meaning that the existing learning motivation variable is normally distributed.

Table 2
Learning Activity Normality Test Results

Amount	Fo	fh	(Fo-fh)	(fo-fh)^2	X^2
31	6	6,0833	-0,0833	0,00694	0,001142
36	6	6,0833	-0,0833	0,00694	0,001142
39	5	6,0833	-1,0833	1,17361	0,192922
41	4	6,0833	-2,0833	4,34028	0,71347
42	9	6,0833	2,9167	8,50694	1,398402
44	8	6,0833	1,9167	3,67361	0,603881
45	13	6,0833	6,9167	47,84028	7,864155
46	11	6,0833	4,9167	24,17361	3,973744
49	7	6,0833	0,9167	0,84028	0,138128
51	3	6,0833	-3,0833	9,50694	1,562785
57	3	6,0833	-3,0833	9,50694	1,562785
59	6	6,0833	-0,0833	0,00694	0,001142
62	2	6,0833	-4,0833	16,67361	2,740868
63	13	6,0833	6,9167	47,84028	7,864155
64	6	6,0833	-0,0833	0,00694	0,001142
65	7	6,0833	0,9167	0,84028	0,138128
66	3	6,0833	-3,0833	9,50694	1,562785
67	13	6,0833	6,9167	47,84028	7,864155
68	5	6,0833	-1,0833	1,17361	0,192922
69	7	6,0833	0,9167	0,84028	0,138128
72	4	6,0833	-2,0833	4,34028	0,71347
75	3	6,0833	-3,0833	9,50694	1,562785
84	1	6,0833	-5,0833	25,84028	4.247717
86	1	6,0833	-5,0833	25,84028	4.247717
	146				49.28767

Based on the calculation results in table 1, the Kolmogorov Smirnov value for the learning activity variable is $0.49.28767 > 0.05$, meaning that the learning activity variable is normally distributed.

Hypothesis testing

Simple Linear Regression Test

Student learning motivation on student learning outcomes (X). The influence of student motivation on student learning outcomes is described by the regression equation $\hat{Y} = a + bX$ where a and b can be calculated with the following formula:

$$a = \frac{(\sum Y)(\sum X_1^2) - (\sum X_1)(\sum X_1 Y)}{N(\sum X_1^2) - (\sum X_1)^2}$$

$$= \frac{(7960)(608033) - (9331)(510834)}{146(608033) - (9331)^2} = 43.01$$

$$b = \frac{N(\sum X_1 Y) - (\sum X_1)(\sum Y)}{N(\sum X_1^2) - (\sum X_1)^2}$$

$$= \frac{146(510834) - (9331)(7960)}{146(608033) - (9331)^2} = 0.180$$

From the results of the calculations a and b, the regression equation can be written as follows:

$$\hat{Y} = 43.01 + 0.180$$

1. Complete calculations can be seen in attachment 7

Thus, the simple linear regression equation regarding the influence of student learning motivation and student learning activity on social studies learning outcomes for class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar can be written as the equation

linear regression as follows $\hat{Y} = 43.01 + 0.180$ _ _ _ _ _

Other scores can be calculated in the same way for each given X score.

2. The influence of active student learning on student learning outcomes (Y)

The influence of active student learning on student learning outcomes is described by the regression equation $\hat{Y} = a + bY$ where a and b can be calculated using the following formula:

$$a = \frac{(\sum Y)(\sum X_2^2) - (\sum X_2)(\sum X_2 Y)}{N(\sum X_2^2) - (\sum X_2)^2}$$

$$= \frac{(7960)(608033) - (9331)(510834)}{146(608033) - (9331)^2} = 43.01$$

$$= \frac{N(\sum X_2 Y) - (\sum X_2)(\sum Y)}{N(\sum X_2^2) - (\sum X_2)^2}$$

$$= \frac{146(510834) - (9331)(7960)}{146(608033) - (9331)^2} = 0.180$$

From the results of the calculations a and b, the regression equation can be written as follows:

Thus, the simple linear regression equation regarding student learning activity on social studies learning outcomes for class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar can be written as the following linear regression equation:

$$\hat{Y} = 43.01 + 0.180 \text{ --- } + 0.180 (64) = 54.54$$

Other scores can be calculated in the same way for each given X score .

Multiple linear regression test

**Table 3
Multiple Regression Analysis Test Results**

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)					,000
	Motivation to learn	5,305	2,222	2,386	0.02	,004
	Learning Activeness	0.929	0.027	33.76	3.66	.016

Based on the table above, the constant value (a) in table 4.7 is known to be 51.862 , while the value of learning motivation (b1) is 5.305 and learning activity (b2) is -0.929, so the regression equation is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_n X_n + e$$

$$Y = 51.862 + 5.305 X_1 + 0.929 X_2 + 20.838$$

1. A constant of 51.862 means that the consistent value of the learning outcome variable is 51.862.
2. The regression coefficient X1 is 1.179 and X2 is -1.108 . The regression coefficient is positive, so it can be said that the direction of influence of variable X1 and variable X2 on Y is positive

Partial Test (t)

Table 4 . t Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)					,000
	Motivation to learn	5,305	2,222	2,386	0.02	,004
	Learning Activeness	0.929	0.027	33.76	3.66	.016

The t test is used to determine whether the hypothesis used is accepted or rejected, with a confidence level of 95% or a = 5% with the following conditions:

1. If t count > t table , then the independent variable has an effect on the dependent variable.
2. If t count < t table , then the independent variable has no effect on the dependent variable.

The results of significance testing can also be seen from the magnitude of the significance value obtained, namely:

1. If the significance value is < 0.05 , then the independent variable has a significant influence on the dependent variable.
2. If the significance value is > 0.05 , then the independent variable does not have a significant effect on the dependent variable.

Simultaneous Hypothesis Test (F)

The F test is carried out to find out whether the independent variables together have an influence on the dependent variable. In this case, Fcount is compared with Ftable with the following conditions :

1. If F count $>$ F table , then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted
2. If F count $<$ F table , then Ha is rejected and Ho is rejected.

Table 5 . F Test Results

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2376.74210	1	6491.65	1140.14	3,600
	Residual	11725,12455	33	5.69370		
	Total	14101.86666	34			
a. Dependent Variable: Learning motivation						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Learning activeness						

The significance value is $<$ alpha = 3.60 so it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between variables x and y.

Coefficient of Determination Test

Table 6 . Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,985 ^a	,971	,971	20,838
a. Predictors: (Constant), Learning Motivation				
b. Dependent Variable: Learning Activeness				

1. The correlation value between x_1x_2 and y is 0.971018074 which is included in the strong category.
2. The coefficient of determination value is 0.97101 or 100 % , which means that x can explain y by 100% , the rest is influenced by other factors.

Discussion

Based on the data analysis that has been carried out, the research process shows the research findings. From the description of the research data, the following data were obtained:

To see whether there is a relationship between variable Y and X, differentiate based on a simple linear regression equation with the equation $= 43.01 + 0.180$ The results of the hypothesis test are:

1. Learning motivation has a positive or relevant influence on the learning outcomes of students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar for the 2023/2024 academic year . This means that if the student's learning motivation is sufficient then the student's learning outcomes are sufficient and vice versa. Meanwhile,

the magnitude of the influence between these two variables is (0.02), which means that the influence on student learning motivation is sufficient.

2. There is a significant influence between Student learning activity on student learning outcomes at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar for the 2023/2024 academic year . This means that if student learning activity is sufficient then student learning outcomes are adequate and vice versa. Meanwhile, the magnitude of the influence between these two variables is (3.66) , which means that the influence on students' learning activity is sufficient.
3. Learning motivation and student learning activity together influence learning outcomes, this result can be seen in the F test where the calculated F value (1140.14) > table F value (0.334). The R Square coefficient of determination test is known to be 0, 971, which means that 97.1% of the variables of learning motivation and student learning activity influence student learning outcomes at the SM P Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar school, and the remaining 2.9% is the influence of variables not examined in this research .

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results and discussion in chapter IV, the conclusions that can be put forward in this research are as follows:

There are several conclusions made by researchers based on the research results that have been researched and discussed in the previous chapter , namely as follows:

1. There is a positive and significant influence of learning motivation on learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of learning motivation (0 , 02) > t table value (1, 690) which means that this variable is significant.
2. There is a positive and significant influence on student learning activity on learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of student learning activity (3.66 > t table value (0.334) means that this variable is significant.
3. Learning motivation and student learning activity together influence learning outcomes, this result can be seen in the F test where the calculated F value (1140.14) > table F value (0.334). The R Square coefficient of determination test is known to be 0, 971, which means that 97.1% of the variables of learning motivation and student learning activity influence student learning outcomes at SM P Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar, and the remaining 2.9% is the influence of variables not examined in this research

FURTHER STUDY

As part of the conclusion of this observation, the researcher provides the following suggestions :

1. Motivation and learning activity have a positive or relevant influence on learning outcomes at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar for the 2023/2024 academic year. Therefore, to improve student learning outcomes, pay attention to these two factors to achieve results study at optimal school.
2. Student learning outcomes . If in the future someone makes a similar observation, it should be carried out in a different place, adding the observation variables or adjusting the time during the observation period.

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